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Mindfulness, and Self-Compassion as a Predictors of Psychological Well-Being

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ABSTRACT

The current study aims to know the Mindfulness, and Self-Compassion as a Predictors of Psychological Well-Being. The study sample consisted of 150 males and females (75 females, 75 males) and their age ranged between (25 to 45) years with a standard deviation of (37 ± 7) years. The average education (8-15) was (12.7 ± 2.6) years. The research tools were the five facet mindfulness Questionnaire, Neff self-compassion scale, and Ryff well-Being Scale. The results of the statistical analysis of the data revealed a positive relationship between mindfulness, self – compassion and well-Being. Regression analysis showed that model consist of (Mindfulness and Self – compassion) predicted the psychological well-Being significantly.

INTRODUCTION

Mindfulness related to Mental health, Psychological Well-being and Quality of life (Chambers *et al.*, 2009), academic competence, social skills, decreased symptoms of anxiety and depression disorders. the results of one study revealed that mindfulness training helps improve cognitive performance, emotional regulation and help to Reducing anxiety and depression in clinical and non-clinical samples.

Mindfulness helps to learn a great deal of self-awareness, increase impulse control, and reduce emotional reaction to distressing events, and conscious behaviour includes that the individual is fully connected to what is happening in the present, whether to what is happening In the external world or the inner world, which enables it to respond to events with full awareness, and non-judgmental awareness leads to the existence of patterns of thinking that help reduce emotional interaction with stressful events.

Studies have also shown that mindfulness and mindfulness-based interventions can improve the psychological well-being of college students (Wester *et al.*, 2009). Research has also shown that people who are more self-compassionate report lower depression, lower levels of anxiety. Self-esteem and self-efficacy, compared to less self-compassionate people (Baker & McNulty, 2011) Self-compassion also predicted symptom severity and lower quality of life, self-compassionate people were found to be more accepting of undesirable aspects of their personality in a healthy way, and A key indicator of psychological well-being, and therefore a viable construct for inclusion in mindfulness-based interventions (Van Dam *et al.*, 2011). Self-compassion is associated with a number of positive variables such as achievement of goals, protection from stress, and mastery of learning of learning, disability-related goals, fear of failure, and acceptance, (Babenko *et al.*, 2018; Babenko & Oswald, 2019; Bluth & Eisenlohr-Moul, 2017; Wagner *et al.*,

2017; Wong & Yeung, 2017). The results of research conducted to investigate the relationship between self-compassion and psychological well-being showed that there is a relationship between the two variables, in studies conducted on adolescents (Bluth *et al.*, 2016).

The results of studies that examined the relationship between self-compassion, sanity, and psychological well-being that were conducted on undergraduate and graduate students, concluded that there is a relationship between the variables of current interest (Christie *et al.*, 2017). Compassion itself has psychological benefits related to increased psychological well-being and decreased distress (Neff *et al.*, 2007; Van Dam *et al.*, 2011). Most of the studies conducted focused on one or two variables of interest to the current research, such as psychological well-being and self-compassion, as in the study (Gunnell *et al.*, 2017; Johnson *et al.*, 2017), and other research studies the relationship between psychological well-being and empathy. With the self as in a study (Stallman *et al.*, 2017; Yang & Make, 2017).

Or psychological well-being and sanity as in a study (Allen *et al.*, 2017; Christie *et al.*, 2017; Fischer *et al.*, 2017; Galante *et al.*, 2017). This gives a justification to focus the current research on examining the relationship between the sanity variable and compassion Self and psychological well-being, in addition to examining the predictive role of the variable of prudence and self-compassion in psychological well-being. This gives justification to focus the current research on examining the relationship between mindfulness, self-compassion, and psychological well-Being. In addition to examining the predictive role of the mindfulness and self compassion in psychological well- Being.

METHOD

Participants

The sample consisted of 150 Egyptians participants (75 women, 75 men), Their age ranged between (26-45) years.

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With an average and standard deviation of (37±7) years. The years of education ranged between (8-15) years with mean and standard deviation of (12.7±2.6) years.

Measures

Mindfulness was measured using the 39-item five-facet mindfulness Questionnaire (Baer *et al.*, 2006) consisting of 39 items. The items of scale contain five points Likert type scale array (1 shows never true, 5 represents always true). There are five basic forms designed to determine skills of mindfulness such as observing, descriBeing, acting with awareness, non-judging experience and non-reactivity to inner experience.

The scale revealed excellent construct validity as well as reliable with alpha coefficient is .80 for total scale. Self-Compassion was measured using the 26-item Self-Compassion Scale (Neff, 2003). consists of six subscales of 26 items with positive and negative items. Three subscales with positive items contain self-kindness, common humanity and mindfulness. Three subscales with negative items have self-judgment, isolation and over-identification. Responses on Likert five points scale array as (1 almost never to 5 almost always). High

positive as well as low negative items of self-compassion means high self-compassion. SCS revealed excellent internal reliability along with Cronbach alpha for the total subscale is 0,7.

Psychological Well-Being was measured using the 42-item Psychological Well-Being Scale (Ryff, 1989). The scale measures six areas of PWB: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. Agreement was rated on a 6-point scale from 1 (*strong disagreement*) to 6 (*strong agreement*).

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1

Correlation analysis showed that mindfulness and self-compassion will be positively related to wellbeing, (see Table 1). It was found that mindfulness had a strong positive relationship with Psychological well –Being.

Hypothesis 2

Multiple regression showed that mindfulness and self-compassion Predictors of Psychological well –Being. (see Table 2).

Table:1 Correlation between variables

Variables	Mindfulness	Self-compassion	Psychological well –Being
Mindfulness	1		
Self-compassion	0.47**	1	
Psychological well –Being	0.83**	0.45**	1

Table 2: Regression Analysis of Mindfulness and Self-Compassion Predict

Model	R	R Square	Stander Error	t	sig
1. (Constant) Mindfulness Self -compassion	0.83	0.70	17.9	15.4	0.001

DISCUSSION

The current study aims to know the Mindfulness, and Self-Compassion as Predictors of Psychological well-Being. The findings of the first hypothesis are consistent with the literature as other studies have also found relationships between mindfulness, self-compassion and wellbeing (Brenner, 2018) which aimed to examine the relationship between self-compassion and psychological distress and psychological well-being in a sample of (789) where the results of the study concluded that there is a positive relationship between self-compassion and psychological well-being, and a negative relationship between psychological distress and psychological well-being, and a negative relationship between psychological distress. A positive association was also found between mindfulness and psychological well-being, indicating that those with a high degree of psychological well-being had a higher degree of self-compassion.

The results of the current research agree with the results of the Kuhn study (Kuhn, 2020), which aimed to know the relationship between self-compassion and well-being among people living in a poor environment in the United States of America. The study sample consisted

of (82) adults, and the study tools were represented in the psychological well-being scale. Prepared by Diner, and the measure of mercy in particular was prepared by Neef, and the results of the study concluded that there is a positive relationship between self-compassion and psychological well-being. It also agrees with the findings of Beer and his colleagues, who conducted a study aimed at examining the relationship between sanity, self-compassion and psychological well-being. The results of the study found a positive relationship between prudence and self-compassion, and the results indicated that prudence and self-compassion skills contribute to improving psychological well-being associated with mindfulness exercises.

It also agrees with the findings of (Bluth & Eisenlohr-Moul, 2017) in their study, which aimed to examine the relationship between prudence, self-compassion, and psychological well-being among adolescents. Between stress, anxiety, stress and depression with self-compassion. The results of the comparison between the pre and post measurement also showed a good effect of the training program based on prudence and compassion in particular in improving psychological well-being and symptoms of anxiety, depression and stress among adolescents.

It also agrees with the study of (Rudaz *et al.*, 2022), which aimed to examine the relationship between sanity, self-compassion and psychological well-being. I have a sample of (680) university students, (637 females, and 43 males). In collecting data, the researchers relied on the MAAS scale of sanity, the Reyes scale of self-compassion, the Diener scale of psychological well-being, and the DASS-21 depression scale. The results of the study found a positive relationship between prudence, self-compassion and psychological well-being, and a negative relationship with depression.

The findings of the second hypothesis are consistent with the literature as other studies have also found mindfulness and self-compassion are predictors of Psychological well-Being. The results of the current research agree with the results of the (Miron, 2012) study, which aimed to examine the role of prudence and compassion in predicting mental disorder, health status and psychological well-being, in a sample of (97) university students who were expelled from the university.

The study tools were the five factors scale of sanity prepared by Baer and colleagues, the scale of compassion in particular prepared by Neef, the psychological distress scale prepared by Loved bond, and the health status scale derived from the healthy quality of life scale prepared by Kessler and colleagues. Hierarchical multiple regression analyses indicated that self-compassion is a good predictor of health and psychological well-being, respectively, and that acting consciously, not judging outcomes, and behavioural factors such as a compassionate and unwise attitude toward a person's thoughts and feelings, may be more influential in promoting health and psychological well-being.

It agrees with the results of the study (Soysa & Wilcomb, 2013), which aimed to examine the relationship between prudence and self-compassion, and the role of prudence, self-compassion and gender in predicting depression, anxiety and psychological well-being among university students. The research sample consisted of (204) male and female students, The results of the study concluded that there is a positive relationship between well-being, prudence and self-compassion, and self-compassion and prudence contributed to predicting anxiety, depression, distress and psychological well-being, and gender also had a role in predicting anxiety, depression and psychological well-being.

It also agrees with study (Bluth & Blanton, 2014), which aimed to examine the relationship between prudence and self-compassion in adolescents, the predictive role of prudence and self-compassion in psychological well-being, and prudence as a mediator in the relationship between self-compassion and psychological well-being. The study sample consisted of (67) adolescents from urban secondary schools. The researchers relied on the Bearer's Children and Adolescents Reasoning Scale, The results of the research concluded that there is a positive relationship between prudence and self-compassion and psychological well-being, and the results of the research

also found that both prudence and self-compassion act as mediators with psychological well-being, meaning that prudence and self-compassion have a dynamic role through which the psychological well-being of adolescents is improved.

CONCLUSION

The results of the current research are consistent with the results of previous studies and the theoretical framework, where the results showed through a literature review that there is a close relationship between sanity and self-compassion, as they facilitate and reinforce each other, as models and explanatory theories have shown that both concepts are related to psychological well-being (MacBeth & Gumley, 2012). The individual's sense of reason involves attention that occurs in the moment of consciousness (Kabat-Zinn, 2003), with an attitude of compassion and warmth (Marlatt & Kristell, 1999). Reason also serves as a barrier against the destructive effects of negative self-judgment. Self-compassion is an alternative to negative self-judgment. Having compassion and compassion towards oneself can reduce anxiety and avoidance behaviours, stimulate relaxation and build a sense of connection, safety and trust in others, and thus improve social relationships and other aspects of psychological well-being.

REFERENCES

- Allen, T. D., Henderson, T. G., Mancini, V. S., & French, K. A. (2017). Mindfulness and meditation practice as moderators of the relationship between age and subjective wellbeing among working adults. *Mindfulness*, 8(4), 1055-1063.
- Babenko, O., & Oswald, A. (2019). The roles of basic psychological needs, selfcompassion, and self-efficacy in the development of mastery goals among medical students. *Medical Teacher*, 41(4), 478-481.
- Babenko, O., Mosewich, A., Abraham, J., & Lai, H. (2018). Contributions of Psychological Needs, Self-compassion, leisure-time Exercise, and Achievement Goals to Academic Engagement and exhaustion in Canadian Medical Students. *Journal of Educational Evaluation for Health Professions*, 15.
- Baer, R., Smith, G. T., Hopkins, J., Krietemeyer, J., & Toney, L. (2006). Using self-report assessment methods to explore facets of mindfulness. *Assessment*, 13, 27-45
- Baker, L. R., & McNulty, J. K. (2011). Self-compassion and relationship maintenance: The moderating roles of conscientiousness and gender. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 100(5), 853-873.
- Bluth, K., & Blanton, P. (2014). Mindfulness and Self Compassion: Exploring Pathway to Adolescence Emotional Well Being. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 23(7), 1298-1309.
- Bluth, K., & Eisenlohr-Moul, T. A. (2017). Response to a Mindful Self-compassion Intervention in Teens: A within-person association of Mindfulness, Self-

- Compassion, and Emotional Well-being outcomes. *Journal of Adolescence*, 57, 108-118.
- Bluth, K., Campo, R. A., Futch, W. S., & Gaylord, S. A. (2016). Age and gender differences in the associations of self-compassion and emotional well-being in a large adolescent sample. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 46(4), 840-853.
- Brenner, D. (2018). *The Distinct relationships of Self Compassion and Self Coldness with Psychological Distress and Wellbeing*. Doctoral of Philosophy, Iowa State University.
- Chambers, R., Gullone, E., & Allen, N. (2009). Mindful emotion regulation: An Integrative Review. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 29, 560-572.
- Christie, A. M., Atkins, P. W., & Donald, J. N. (2017). The meaning and doing of Mindfulness: The Role of Values in the link between Mindfulness and Wellbeing. *Mindfulness*, 8(2), 368-378.
- Fisher, S., Zapolski, T., Sheehan, C& Barnes-Najor, J . (2017). Pathway of Protection: Ethnic Identity, Self – Esteem, and Substance use among Multiracial Youth. *Addict Behavior*, 72, 27-32.
- Galante, J., Jones, P. B., Dufour, G., Benton, A., Howarth, E. L., Vainre, M., & Stochl, J. (2017). *A randomized controlled trial of the provision of a Mindfulness Intervention to Support University Students' Wellbeing and resilience to stress: Preliminary results*.
- Gunnell, K. E., Mosewich, A. D., McEwen, C. E., Eklund, R. C., & Crocker, P. R. (2017). Don't be so hard on yourself! Changes in Self-Compassion during the First year of University are associated with Changes in Well-being. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 107, 43-48.
- Johnson, S. B., Goodnight, B. L., Zhang, H., Daboin, I., Patterson, B., & Kaslow, N. J. (2017). Compassion-based Meditation in African Americans: Self-Criticism Mediates Changes in Depression. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 48(2), 160-168. Retrieved from: <http://psychiatry.emory.edu/>
- Kabat-Zinn, J. (2003). Mindfulness-based Intervention in Context: Past, Present, and Future. *Clinical Psychology: Science and Practice*, 10, 144-156.
- Kuhn, K. (2020). *Correlation between Subjective Well-Being and Self-Compassion in Individuals Living in Poverty*. Doctorate of Education. Grand Canyon University.
- MacBeth, A., & Gumley, A. (2012). Exploring compassion: A meta- analysis of the association between self – compassion and psychopathology. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 32(6), 545-552.
- Marlatt, G.A., & Kristeller, J.L. (1999). Mindfulness and Mediation. In W.R . Miller (Ed), *Integrating spirituality into treatment*, 67-84. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Miron, L. (2012). *A Comparison of Self Compassion and Mindfulness in Predicting Psychological Distress*, Health Status and Wellbeing. Master Degree. North Illinois University.
- Neff, K. D. (2003). *The Development and Validation of a scale to Measure self- Compassion , Self Identity*, 2(3), 223-250.
- Neff, K. D., Rude, S. S., & Kirkpatrick, K. (2007). An Examination of Self-compassion in relation to Positive Psychological Functioning and Personality Traits. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 41, 908-916.
- Rudaz, M., Ledermann, T., & Fincham, F. (2022). Caring for bliss Moderates the association between Mindfulness, Self-Compassion and Well Being in Collage Attending EmerBeing Adultes. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*.
- Ryff, C. D. (1989). Happiness is everything, or is it? Explorations on the meaning of psychological well-being. *Journal of Personality and Social Ppsychology*, 57(6), 1069-1081.
- Soysa, C., & Wilcomb, C. (2013). *Mindfulness , self – Compassion , Self-Efficacy , and Gender Predictors of Depression , Anxiety, Stress and Well- Being*. Mindfulness.
- Stallman, H. M., Ohan, J. L., & Chiera, B. (2017). The role of social support, being present and self-kindness in university student well-being. *British Journal of Guidance & Counselling*, 1-10.
- Van Dam, N. T., Sheppard, S. C., Forsyth, J. P., & Earleywine, M. (2011). Self-compassion is a better Predictor than Mindfulness of Symptom Severity and Quality of life in mixed Anxiety and Depression. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 25(1), 123-130.
- Wagner, L. K., Schindler, S., & Reinhard, M. A. (2017). The Positive Facet of Self-Compassion Predicts Self-reported use of and Attitudes toward Desirable Difficulties in learning. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 1353.
- Wester, K., Trepal, H., & Meyers, J. (2009). Wellness of Counselor Educators: An Initial look. *Journal of Humanistic Counseling, Education & Development*, 48, 92-111.
- Wong, C. C. Y., & Yeung, N. C. (2017). Self-compassion and posttraumatic growth: Cognitive processes as mediators. *Mindfulness*, 1-10.
- Yang, X., & Mak, W. W. (2017). The Differential Moderating Roles of Self-Compassion and Mindfulness in Self-stigma and Well-being among People Living with Mental Illness or HIV. *Mindfulness*, 8(3), 595-602.